

DESIGN OF MOBILE PUBLIC KEY INFRASTRUCTURE (M-PKI) USING ELLIPTIC CURVE CRYPTOGRAPHY

Sangram Ray¹ and G. P. Biswas²

¹Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad-826004, India

sangram.ism@gmail.com

²Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad-826004, India

gpbiswas@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Recently the demand of mobile phones and their applications are increasing rapidly and as a result, it becomes essential to design and/or improve the existing PKI (Public Key Infrastructure) useful for mobile phones or devices. Since a mobile phone has small screen, low computing power, small storage capacity etc, the present paper proposes an ECC-based mobile-PKI that overcomes these limitations and supports various mobile-based applications, because the use of ECC significantly reduces the computation cost, message size and transmission overhead over RSA based PKI as 160-bit key-size in ECC provides comparable security with 1024-bit key in RSA. Also the proposed method includes a Mobile Home Agent (MHA) per user and a Registration Authority (RA) that further minimize the major work/processing loads of mobile phone and Certificate Authority (CA), respectively. This paper addresses a secure implementation of the proposed M-PKI, whose security analysis against different attacks shows that all attacks are protected. Finally, a comparative study of the M-PKI with the existing PKI is done, which gives satisfactory performance.

KEYWORDS

Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC), Public Key Infrastructure (PKI), Wireless Application Protocol (WAP), Certificate Authority (CA), Registration Authority (RA), Mobile Home Agent (MHA), Wireless Certificate Management Protocol (WCMP)

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, different Internet-based e-services have been deploying for several applications and their facilities help people to lead comfortable lives, and such utilities can be further extended if the e-services are accessible with low-cost and easily deployable infrastructure like mobile phones/devices. As a result, even during their mobility, the mobile users can now access the internet through wireless communication using mobile phones for their information, recourses, data etc. very easily. Also different mobile applications like in banking, payment, business, health care, voting are in use and developing. However, the security aspect in wireless/mobile technology as such has not been considered and it becomes a great concern for mobile users to successfully utilize the electronic services through the wireless systems. Generally, five different fundamental security functions like confidentiality, data integrity, entity authentication, availability and non-repudiation are considered for an application to be secured and thus to support these security functions to mobile phone as well as wireless environment, the

development of mobile-PKI is needed, where a PKI provides initial security associations among arbitrary entities based on which actual security functions are applied [1-5].

The well established PKI in wired environment [5, 6, 7] is mainly used to generate a public key certificate for a user containing a valid and authenticate public key with its owner's identity and validity period, and the same is used for secure negotiation of cryptographic parameters. To get a certificate from PKI, the CMP (Certificate Management Protocol) supports the online interactions between PKI user and management entities. It is also used to carry the user's registration information and certificate revocation request. However, it is difficult to use wired PKI in wireless environment since wireless internet [4, 7, 8] has lower transmission bandwidth and mobile phone has fundamental limitations like small screen size, low computing power, low memory capacity, [5, 7, 9, 10, 11] etc. Hence, the requirement of PKI/CMP suitable for mobile environment must be developed for mobile-PKI to guarantee security of different mobile applications.

In recent era, WAP (Wireless Application Protocol) is used in mobile phone to access wireless internet and several extensions of WAP such as WAP 1.x, WAP 2.0 [6] etc. are proposed. Among them, the WAP 1.x [5, 8] is applied in wireless internet, where WTLS (Wireless Transport Layer Protocol), equivalent to SSL (Secure Socket Layer) of the wired internet, is in-charge of security. However, the WTLS can't support end-to-end security since in WAP, data must go through the WAP gateway that decodes the WTLS's encrypted data before it is encrypted using SSL and transmitted to the server and inversely, the data encrypted with SSL is decoded by the WAP gateway before it is encrypted with WTLS and sent to mobile phone. This causes a serious security problem in the gateway [5, 7, 12] since WTLS could not support the confidentiality of certificate request message. Another problem of WAP is that it does not support POP (Proof of Possession) [11, 13, 14] function in its certificate request message.

To remove these problems, Y. Lee et al. [15, 16] proposed a wireless CMP suitable for wireless PKI in 2007 and 2008 where a mobile phone securely requests a public key certificate to CA (Certificate Authority). After receiving the request, CA performs the user authentication and verifies the POP function, which means that the mobile phone has generated the valid private key corresponding to the public key. If the verification passes, CA publishes the certificate on its directory or WEB and should give a certificate or certificate URL to the mobile user. Some of the limitations of this scheme are observed such as it requires an out-of-band user identification at CA to collect an ID and password for certificate request which is not realistic. Also, the mobile phone generates the certificate request message itself, which may not be always possible for a device like mobile phone that has less memory and less powerful CPU.

To overcome these limitations, we propose a MHA (Mobile Home Agent) based mobile-PKI (M-PKI) using elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) in this paper, where MHA performs all cryptographic operations in favour of mobile phone. In our scheme, instead of RSA, ECC [19-21] is used which provides same security of RSA with comparatively less processing time and less key size, for instance, a 1024-bit key in RSA is equivalent with 160-bit in ECC. Moreover, a MHA holds the full responsibility on behalf of mobile phone to store all the cryptographic information of mobile phone and performs all the operations to get a certificate from CA. A Registration Authority (RA) is also considered to minimize the work load of CA where RA performs the user authentication and POP verification procedure instead of CA. If the verification passes, RA approved the certificate request message and sends it to CA with attestation. After receiving, CA checks the attestation of RA of the certificate request message and then creates the ECC-based public key certificate of mobile phone, signs on it, and publishes the certificate in its directory and finally, gives a certificate URL to MHA. After receiving, MHA only forwards the

certificate URL to the mobile phone, and the mobile phone user uses the URL for authentication and any secret value negotiation with other entity through open channel.

The remaining parts of this paper are organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the Elliptic Curve Cryptography, its computational problems and the CA/RA for issuing and management of ECC-based public key certificate. The proposed M-PKI using ECC is given in section 3, whose security analysis is described in section 4. Section 5 provides a comparison results with the existing schemes that shows improved performance, and finally, the paper is concluded in section 6.

2. PRELIMINARIES

To facilitate of our proposed scheme, the following articles are briefly introduced.

2.1. Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC)

The elliptic curve cryptosystem [18, 19] was initially proposed by Koblitz [20] and then Miller [21] in 1985 to design public key cryptosystem and presently, it becomes an integral part of the modern cryptography. A brief introduction of ECC is given below:

Let E/F_p denotes an elliptic curve E over a prime finite field F_p , which can be defined by

$$y^2 = x^3 + ax + b \quad (1)$$

where, $a, b \in F_p$ and the discriminant $D = 4a^3 + 27b^2 \neq 0$

The points on E/F_p together with an extra point O called the point at infinity used for additive identity form an additive group A as

$$A = \{(x, y) : x, y \in F_p, E(x, y) = 0\} \cup \{O\} \quad (2)$$

Let n , the order of A , is very large and it can be defined as $n \times G \text{ mod } q = O$, where G is the generator of A . Also A be a cyclic additive group under the point addition “+” defined as

$$P + O = P, \text{ where } P \in A.$$

The scalar point multiplication over A can be defined as

$$tP = P + P + \dots + P \text{ (t times)} \quad (3)$$

If $P, Q \in A$, the addition $P + Q$ be a point $-R$ (whose inverse is R with only changing the sign of y coordinate value and lies on the curve) on the E/F_p such that all the points P, Q and $-R$ lie on the straight line, i.e., the straight line cuts the curve at P, Q and $-R$ points. Note that if $P = Q$, it becomes a tangent at P or Q , which is assumed to intersect the curve at the point O .

The security strength of the ECC lies on the difficulty of solving the Elliptic Curve Discrete Logarithm Problem (ECDLP) [19-21] and it provides same level of security of RSA with less bit-size key, which is addressed in the next sub-section.

2.2. Computational problems

Similar to the DH problem (known as discrete logarithm problem) [22], some computational hard problems on ECC are defined below, which have not any polynomial time algorithm.

- **Elliptic Curve Discrete Logarithm Problem (ECDLP)**

Given $Q, R \in A$, find an integer $k \in F_p^*$ such that $R = kQ$.

- **Computational Diffie-Hellman Assumption (CDHA)**

Given $P, xP, yP \in A$, it is hard to compute $xyP \in A$.

- **Decisional Diffie-Hellman Problem (DDHP)**

Given $P, aP, bP, cP \in G$ for any $a, b, c \in F_p^*$, decide whether or not $cP = abP$.

2.3. CA, RA and ECC based certificate

A CA [13], which is the base of a PKI, is a trusted agency that issues digital certificates for the verification and validation of users' public keys with the owners of the certificates. The entities individually contact with a CA by providing their identity such as name, address, date of birth, public key etc of each entity and after validation through handshake procedure, the CA performs some level of entity authentication according to Certificate Practices Statement (CPS) [17] and then issues a digital certificate containing the entity's identity and public key for each entity. The entities can now exchange the certificates among themselves and become authenticated to each other which assure the receiving of the authenticated public keys of the entities.

To minimize the workload of CA, many PKI considers the existence of a Registration Authority (RA) [13] separated from the CA to perform authentication, verification, distribution, revocation reporting etc. where each RA being certified by CA has both authenticated private and public keys for works together with CA.

The Public-Key Infrastructure working group of Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) similar to the X.509 RSA based public key certificate [24-28], specifies ECC based public key certificate standardized as the PKI-X.509. Subsequently, the Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA), Elliptic Curve Diffie-Hellman (ECDH) public keys and the generation of ECC based certificate with ECDSA signature of PKIX are proposed in [23, 27, 28]. Note that the ECC-based PKIX is easily interoperable with RSA-based PKI (X.509) and the Certificate Authority (CA) issues and certifies ECC-based certificates. A simple ECC-based X.509 certificate format [23] to combine user's identity and the ECC-based public key proposed by ITU (International Telecommunication Union) is described in figure 1.

Figure 1. ECC-based X.509 certificate format

2.4. Certificate management protocol

The Certificate Management Protocol holds the online interactions between PKI user and management entities such as RA/CA. It manages the life cycle of the certificate through initial issue, renewal, suspension and revocation, which are briefly described below [15, 16].

2.4.1. Initial issue of certificate

The initial certificate request protocol has five steps as follows:

- Step 1:* User generates a public-private key pair and sends a certificate request message to CA.
- Step 2:* CA receives the request and checks the certificate request message.
- Step 3:* CA performs the user authentication.
- Step 4:* CA checks the user must possess a private key corresponding to the public key received.
- Step 5:* CA issues the public key certificate to the user.

2.4.2. Renewal of key pair and certificate

The renewal of the user's key pair is required when the private key has been damaged, lost, leaked or stolen. To get an updated key pair, the user sends a key pair renewal request together with his public key and information for POP to CA, which also updates the certificate during renewal of the key pair. On the other hand, in case of certificate renewal, a user sends his certificate update request to CA before the certificate expiration date for maintaining the validity of the certificate.

2.4.3. Suspension and revocation of certificate

The certificate suspension request is sent by the user to CA only when he suspects that his private key has been damaged, lost, leaked or stolen. Later, he checks the security of the certificate and depending upon the outcome he takes any one of the following steps: 1) If the user realizes that his private key has not damaged, lost, leaked or stolen, then he sends the certificate reuse request to CA and to change the status of the certificate as valid which make him able to reuse the same public key as the key pair and the certificate, 2) If user be sure that his private key has been damaged, lost, leaked or stolen, then he sends the certificate revocation request to CA to revoke

his certificate and as a result, CA revokes that certificate and includes it in its CRL (Certificate Revocation List) [17].

3. THE PROPOSED ECC BASED M-PKI

The proposed ECC-based M-PKI is described in this section, which as stated before, is more efficient than RSA-based PKI in terms of computation and communication cost and key size used with comparable security. Similar to mobile internet, a MHA, which is considered to overcome the fundamental limitations of mobile phone, stores all the information of mobile phone and performs all the operations to get a certificate of mobile phone from CA. Moreover, a trusted RA is also considered to minimize the work load of CA such as user authentication and POP verification procedures.

3.1. Mobile public key certificate management procedure

The proposed MHA based Certificate Management Procedure is discussed below, where a workflow diagram is shown in figure 2 for visual illustration.

Figure 2. Workflow diagram of proposed certificate management procedure

Step 1: MHA generates an ECC-based public-private key pair for the mobile phone and sends it to RA as a *certificate request message* along with others relevant information to get the public key certificate of mobile phone from CA.

Step 2: After receiving, RA authenticates MHA and verifies the POP function to be sure that the user possess a private key corresponding to the public key for which a certificate being requested. If the verification passes, RA approves the *certificate request* message and sends it to CA with attestation for generating the certificate.

Step 3: CA checks whether the *certificate request* message is attested by RA, if so, CA creates the public key certificate, signs it, and publishes the certificate in its directory.

Step 4: CA generates the certificate, stores it at CA-directory and sends a *certificate URL* to MHA.

Step 5: On receiving, MHA forwards the same to the mobile phone along with the mobile phone's private key encrypted using the pre-shared secret key k .

Now, the mobile phone user gets the *certificate URL* and decrypts the encrypted private key using the pre-shared secret key k and gets his private key.

3.2. Certificate request message generation and verification

Initially, MHA of a mobile phone user collects the public key of a RA and generates a certificate request message with an ECC-based public-private key pair $(s_1, V_1 = s_1P)$ and then, sends it to RA. After receiving, RA verifies the certificate request message after prior mutual authentication and forwards to CA with attestation. The details of the *certificate request message generation and verification* procedure (say, *cert-gen-verify*) is given below, where the following notations are used.

- $h(.)$ One-way hash function such as SHA1;
- ID_{MHA} Identity of mobile home agent
- ID_M Identity of mobile phone
- $//$ Concatenation
- p, n Two large prime numbers;
- Fp A finite field;
- E An elliptic curve defined on Fp with prime order n ;
- P A point on elliptic curve E with order n ;
- (s_1, V_1) Private/public key pair of MHA, where $V_1 = s_1P$;
- (s_2, V_2) Private/public key pair of RA, where $V_2 = s_2P$;

Procedure: *cert-gen-verify*

Step 1: MHA → RA: $M // E_{K_x} (H // R_1)$

Certificate request message M is generated by MHA by concatenating its identity, mobile phone's identity and public key and the hash digest of the same is computed as $M = ID_{MHA} // ID_M // V_1$ and $H = h(M)$. Now it selects a random number r_1 and generates $R_1 = r_1.P$ and also calculates an ECDH session key $K = s_1.V_2 = s_1.s_2.P = (K_x, K_y)$. Then MHA concatenates the hash digest of M with R_1 , encrypts the concatenated message using K_x , concatenates M with the encrypted message and then sends the concatenated message to RA as a certificate request message.

Step 2: RA → MHA: $R_1 + R_2, E_{K_x} (ID_{RA} // h(R_2))$

After receiving the certificate request message, RA gets the identity of MHA and mobile phone and also gets the public key of the mobile phone from M for which the certificate is requested. Now it calculates the hash digest H of received M as $H = h(M)$ and the ECDH session key using mobile phone's public key as $K = s_2.V_1 = (K_x, K_y)$, decrypts the encrypted message using K_x , gets H and R_1 and then, compares the received H with calculated H . If both match, then RA confirms that the MHA have generated the private key for the corresponding public key i.e. POP function is verified. Now, for authentication purposes, RA selects a random number r_2 and generates $R_2 = r_2.P$, calculates the hash digest of R_2 as $h(R_2)$, encrypts its identity and the hash digest using K_x and then sends the encrypted message along with $(R_1 + R_2)$ to MHA for authentication.

Certificate issuance: After receiving the verified and attested certificate request message M from RA, CA verifies for confirmation and then generates the ECC-based public key certificate of mobile phone, signs it using ECDSA, publishes the certificate in its directory and finally, sends the *certificate URL* to MHA.

Life cycle: The M-PKI supports not only the initial issue of mobile phone’s certificate but also includes update of key pair, certificate, certificate suspension and revocation. For these, a common message with a *request for type-update* is used to define the type of the certificate request made to CA. The different message formats for certificate life cycle are given in table 1.

Table 1. Message formats of certificate life cycle.

Life cycle	Message M with update-type
Initial issue	$M = \text{initial issue} \parallel \text{ID}_{\text{MHA}} \parallel \text{ID}_{\text{M}} \parallel V_1$
Key pair update	$M = \text{key pair update} \parallel \text{ID}_{\text{MHA}} \parallel \text{ID}_{\text{M}} \parallel V_{1 \text{ New}}$
Certificate update	$M = \text{certificate update} \parallel \text{certificate serial No.} \parallel \text{ID}_{\text{MHA}} \parallel \text{ID}_{\text{M}} \parallel V_1$
Certificate suspension	$M = \text{certificate suspension} \parallel \text{certificate serial No.} \parallel \text{ID}_{\text{MHA}} \parallel \text{ID}_{\text{M}} \parallel V_1$
Certificate revocation	$M = \text{certificate revocation} \parallel \text{certificate serial No.} \parallel \text{ID}_{\text{MHA}} \parallel \text{ID}_{\text{M}} \parallel V_1$

3.4. Certificate verification

An existing hierarchical tree structure of CAs comprising a root CA and a number of intermediate CAs at different level of the hierarchy tree is considered [17, 18] in our proposed M-PKI for certificate issuance, distribution, revocation and verification, and such a M-PKI model with three hierarchies is illustrated in figure 4. Note that the leaf nodes of a CA hierarchical tree are always users like MHA and/or application server that wish to get the certificates or to verify other’s certificate.

Figure 4. M-PKI hierarchical model

The root CA has a self-signed and self-issued certificate, which is distributed to its adjacent intermediates CAs for the verification of the public key of the root CA. The intermediate CAs like CA_1, CA_2, \dots, CA_m receive their certificates from the root CA and become trusted to each other through the root CA. Thus, any CA can verify the public key of other CAs through the certificate of the root CA. In this regard, a notation of the trustiness such as $X \ll Y \gg$ is used, where X is a root (or an intermediate CA) and Y is an intermediate CA or a user. Now the meaning of the

trustiness representation is that X has issued a certificate for Y . As in figure 4, any user $User1$ (say) can have a valid certificate chain if the following notation exists:

$$root\ CA \ll CA1 \gg \text{ and } CA1 \ll User1 \gg$$

It means that $User1$ is verified through the certificate of $CA1$, which is then verified by the root CA . In this way, any user at any level of the CA hierarchy tree can be cryptographically verified for his public key [18].

Note that, in our scheme, MHA and application server exchanged their certificate URL for mutual authentication. The certificate URL is then used to get certificate of each other from CA directory and finally the received certificate is verified by each other as stated above.

3.5. Certificate validation and applications

After receiving the *certificate URL* and private key from MHA , the mobile phone user utilizes the certificate URL for different mobile applications and generic workflow diagram is shown in figure 5. Initially, a mobile phone user sends a *transaction request type* to MHA , which then identifies the server-URL on searching and sends the certificate URL of the mobile-phone user to the server for making an authenticated and secure channel for transactions to be made between them. However, before any transaction, the application server retrieves the certificate of mobile phone from the CA directory using the certificate URL and acquires the CRL for validation of the certificate. Similarly, the server sends its certificate URL and CA 's certificate together to MHA for the validation of the server. After completion of the both side validation procedure, MHA and the application server uses the valid certificates to make an authenticated secure channel between them for the required transaction.

Figure 5. Proposed certificate validation and application procedure in M-PKI

4. SECURITY ANALYSIS

In our proposed ECC-based M-PKI, initially, MHA should be authenticated to RA to ensure that the mobile user possess the valid private key of corresponding public key. And once the certificate is issued by CA through RA and used by the mobile phone user, the mutual authentication of both server and mobile user must also be established. Thus the proposed ECC-based M-PKI involves the following cryptographic operations, where shown briefly that all are well protected.

Moreover, the proposed ECC-based scheme provides low computation and communication cost as well as less key-size to provide same level of security as of RSA, and thus it is efficient as explained below.

Mutual authentication: After receiving the certificate request message, RA verifies the message, completes the mutual authentication and then forwards the message to CA with attestation. The detail procedure of mutual authentication is discussed in steps 1 to 4 of *section 3.3* which assure that before issuing a certificate, the RA must authenticates the MHA/user.

POP verification: The POP verification procedure is considered in our scheme which ensures that the mobile user possesses the private key of corresponding public key. The verification procedure is done in our scheme by calculating K and comparing hash digests at step 2 of *section 3.3*.

Confidentiality: MHA sends the mobile phone's private key encrypted using the pre-shared secret key k . Mobile phone gets his private key after decrypting it using the pre-shared secret key k . So, the private key of the mobile phone is securely transmitted to mobile phone from MHA as explained in step 5 of *section 3.1*.

Replay attack prevention: To prevent replay attack in our scheme, MHA sends the public key to RA only once and each mobile phone has different public key. If the same public key is applied twice, RA should realize the possibility of replay attack and as a result, terminates the process.

Efficiency: The proposed ECC-based M-PKI is more efficient than the existing RSA-based schemes due to the following reasons:

- (1) *Provides comparable security with small key-length:* In general, 160-bit key in ECC is equivalent in security with 1024-bit key in RSA [19, 20, 21]. This is because, the existing RSA based mobile-PKI uses Diffie–Hellman key exchange algorithm [22] in which the required public challenges are generated by using 1024 bits key length to make it secure. Where as in ECC, public challenges are of 160 bits key length which is much less than RSA to provide same security level.
- (2) *Requires less computation cost:* The computation cost of elliptic curve scalar point multiplication is much less than that of modular exponentiation used in RSA since the expensive modular exponentiation is used over 1024-bit discrete logarithm problem (DLP) but elliptic curve scalar point multiplication is over 160-bit ECDLP [19, 20, 21]. Although, the proposed scheme uses the general cryptographic hash function and elliptic curve multiplication/addition, which is quite slower operation, but instead of RSA-based public key encryption (having slower processing speed) the ECC-based symmetric key encryption (faster) is used. Therefore, the proposed ECC based M-PKI requires less computation cost than the existing RSA based mobile-PKI. and
- (3) *Requires less communication cost:* Due to less key-size, the message-size is reduced and the number of messages used with respect to the mobile phone users is less due to the use of MHA.

5. COMPARISON

Finally, the proposed scheme is compared with other two existing schemes and the outputs are shown in table 2, which shows that the proposed scheme is only ECC based and achieves all six parameters considered.

Table 2. Comparison of proposed schemes with existing schemes

Parameters	WAP [5,8]	Y. Lee et al.[15,16]	Proposed protocol
Cryptosystem	RSA	RSA	ECC
End-to-end security	No	Yes	Yes
Confidentiality	No	Yes	Yes
Absence of out-of-band user identification	Yes	No	Yes
POP verification	No	Yes	Yes
Overcomes the fundamental limitations of mobile phone	No	No	Yes
Supports less computation and communication overhead	No	No	Yes
Key size require to provide comparable security	1024 bits	1024 bits	160 bits

6. CONCLUSION

This paper addresses the design of an ECC-based M-PKI usable for mobile phones/devices. For this, some modifications of the existing PKI have been done and they are incorporation of ECC for short-length keys/messages and low computation/communication costs, introduction of a MHA per mobile user for bearing most of the certificate related burden and a RA to work in association with a CA. We also propose the use of a specific URL by mobile phone/MHA for the certificate downloading/ verification through the CA directories thereby solving the memory requirement for certificate storage and others. The security analysis, processing efficiency and the comparison of the proposed schemes with the existing PKI schemes have been done and it has been found that the proposed M-PKI is well secured and fit for mobile phones with any application.

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Authors

Sangram Ray has obtained B.Sc (Hons.) degree in Mathematics from University of Burdwan, West Bengal, India in 2005, and M.Sc in Mathematics and Computing and M.Tech. in Computer Application from Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad, India in 2007 and 2009 respectively. Currently he is a Senior Research Fellow in the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad, India and pursuing Ph.D. in Computer Science and Engineering in the same university. His main research interests include Cryptography, Network/Information Security and Computer Networks.

G.P. Biswas has obtained B.Sc (Engg.) and M.Sc (Engg.) degrees in Electrical & Electronics Engineering and Computer Science & Engineering, respectively; and obtained his Ph.D. degree in Computer Science & Engineering from Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India. Currently he is a Professor in the Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Indian school of Mines, Dhanbad, India. He has around 20 years of teaching and research experience, where he teaches a number of UG/PG papers including Theory of Computation, Computer Org/Arch, Computer Networks, VLSI Designs, Cryptography and Network Security, etc. He has published around 70 research papers in Journals and Conference/Seminar Proceedings. Prof. Biswas has guided B.Tech/M.Tech and Ph.D. students for their dissertations and PhD degrees, respectively. His research interests include Cryptography, Network security, Cellular Automata, VLSI designs, Computer Networks and Wireless Communication.

